

15 April 2024

Artificial Intelligence Threat Reporting & Incident Response System

Advanced cybersecurity for smart cities will be made possible with IRIS project!

The first wave of the project's Pilot Use Cases (PUCs) have concluded successfully! IRIS EU project, held the first part of its three Pilot Use Cases in March 2024 and received valuable feedback from the stakeholders who participated.

Improving cybersecurity for smart cities is a major advancement that will be made possible by the IRIS project! Completing the first wave of the project's three Pilot Use Cases in March 2024 was the first step we took to showcase the capabilities of the IRIS technology solution and evaluate the project's tools.

PUC 1 held on 7 March 2024, led by the Municipal Institute of Information ([IMI](#)), at [CISCO](#) premises in Barcelona, Spain. The focus of the 1st PUC was to secure the IoT and control system infrastructure deployed in the tramway station against confidentiality and integrity breaches, promoting safety and security in urban environments and ensuring that trams, pedestrians and bikes can interact safely by mitigating the accidents resulting from man-made cyber-attacks.

[Forum Virium Helsinki](#) led and organized PUC 3, which took place online on 21 March 2024. During the event, consortium partners demonstrated the capabilities of Virtual Cyber Range in training CERTs/CSIRTs and validated the capabilities of the IRIS platform in safeguarding the Helsinki Smart Grid environment against cyber threats and vulnerabilities.

PUC 2 was the last to be held on 27 March 2024, also remotely. The pilot use case was led by the [Finest Centre for Smart Cities](#) with the aim of protecting the AI-enabled

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infrastructure of the autonomous transport system (AV shuttle and the Remote Operation Centre) available in Tallinn against potential orchestrated attacks.

Besides the IRIS consortium partners, several stakeholders from national CERTs, the transportation sector and vulnerable road users, the telecommunication and energy sector and representatives from different municipalities attended the pilot and gave useful feedback regarding not only the technical parts but also about the societal acceptance that is an important element of the project.

The second and final part of the three Pilot Use Cases will be finalized by August 2024.

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Project at a Glance

Acronym	IRIS
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Funding	This project has received funding from from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 101021727
Duration	36 months (September 2021 – August 2024)
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